

ART STUDIES

THE ISSUES OF WORD FORMATION IN THE ACTOR'S CREATIVE PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In the scientific article, the authors considered one of the main problems of stage speech - the features of the process of word formation and ways to develop it. In general, it is known that the language of the stage has a special place in the art of acting. This is because the five sections, which are the basis of the stage language, have a great role to play. Speaking on stage is one thing, word formation is another. While it is not easy to speak, the task of creating words is even more difficult and responsible for an actor. He was taught the language of the scene. Stage language, along with actors, is a subject that develops the speaking skills of directors, TV and radio presenters, lecturers, team leaders and public figures, as well as lawyers and judges. The authors of the scientific article analyzed the topic with many examples. For example, he analyzes the peculiarities of its pronunciation on the stage, quoting from the literary works of classical writers. Speaking on stage on a piece of paper, that is, the process of birth of the word, is widely discussed. In addition, it is clearly stated that the main parts of the stage language - diction, breathing, voice, orthoepy, work with the text are very useful in the process of word formation on stage. The method and method of learning the word is very similar and common for drama theater actors, musical theater actors, chamber or pop artists, opera artists, masters of rhetoric. Creating words on stage begins with controlling your inner feelings and mental agility. Avoiding the search for phonetics in speech, on the contrary, will only succeed if you try to reveal the psychology of the character. After all, through the word comes the image of the character. Speech skills and speech activity are mainly developed through the sense organs that influence the process of word formation. In particular, the process of word formation on stage begins with the development of speech techniques, recognition of the speech apparatus, mastering the breath and voice. Similarly, the authors of the article professionally analyze the internal and external words, which are important in the process of word formation, and provide evidence.

Keywords: word, stage speech, voice, diction, actor, acting skills, effective word.

The process of creating speech on stage begins with controlling inner feelings and the sharpness of thought. When speaking, one should avoid searching for phonetic precision; instead, striving to reveal the psychology of the character is the key to success. Because through speech, character traits emerge — and from character, the image of the persona is born. The art of speech and speech activity generally unfold through the sensory organs that influence the process of generating words. We rely on K. S. Stanislavski's well-known system of the "Five Senses" — sight, hearing, touch, taste, and smell. Considering these theoretical principles, we move to the act of speech. For a student or actor creating a role, this system has tremendous importance. The actor should not only reproduce what they have seen or heard but must also generate what they have never seen or heard through the imagination.

Speaking on stage is one thing, but creating speech is quite another. Even mastering proper delivery is not easy, while for an actor, the ability to generate authentic speech is an even more complex and responsible task. This is taught through stage speech. Stage speech is a discipline that refines not only actors but also directors, television and radio presenters, lecturers, public leaders, as well as advocates and judges — anyone whose profession requires mastery of speech.

For example, one of the five main components of stage speech is working with a text. At this stage, future actors learn to read everything from short texts to monologues. A monologue must be expressive, emotionally rich, and delivered with artistic intonation. It should

fully reveal the image, character, and speech style (and even the cultural and spiritual background) of the persona.

To achieve this, the student must not recite the author's words mechanically or decorate them externally, but rather express them as if they originated from their own feelings and thoughts — in other words, speak as though the words are their own.

Let us illustrate this with an excerpt from S. Zhūnisov's novel "Aqan Seri", where Aqan speaks at Qadisha's funeral before a crowd of people:

Aqan: "You keep saying Fediya, Fediya! Which of you dares, without trembling, to speak of the trade made with the untimely death of a pure soul? You, vultures fattened on death, grave mice and jackals gnawing bones in the tombs, you who bow and chant at the sight of carrion! You, whose faces shine while your hearts are filled with poison, reciting verses with unclean tongues, mocking life itself as you hoard zakat and ransom money — you, hypocrites and soulless creatures, pretending to pray daily while hiding your sins!" [1, p. 262]. To convey Aqan's anguish and his condemnation of the hypocrisy of his contemporaries — the greedy clerics and false believers — the actor must work with deep emotion and intensity. The student or actor who reads this monologue should express such passion that the audience feels it in their very bones. Here, the harmony of emotion and imagination, the ability to visualize the scene internally — to make the audience see the moral decay — is essential. All of this depends on mastery of speech technique and performance skill.

The methods and approaches to mastering speech are similar for dramatic actors, musical and opera performers, reciters, and variety artists. Developing speech technique begins with understanding the speech apparatus, mastering breathing, and training the voice. Let us examine these three components separately.

1. The Function of the Speech Apparatus

The human speech apparatus is a complex and fascinating mechanism, both in structure and function, and mastering it professionally is crucial. It consists of two groups of organs:

1. Movable organs — lips, tongue, lower jaw, soft palate, uvula.

2. Immovable organs — upper jaw, teeth, deeper jawbones, tooth sockets.

The Process of Speech Production

During speech, the air from the lungs, that is, the breath, passes through the respiratory tract and reaches the esophagus, where it touches the vocal cords (ligaments), causing them to vibrate and thus turning the breath into sound. When this sound reaches the oral cavity, depending on the position of the movable organs of the speech apparatus mentioned above, the sound becomes either a vowel or a consonant. Two or three sounds form a syllable or a word. When pronouncing each word, syllable, or letter, the speech apparatus changes its position in various ways.

Example 1: Let us take the word “TOP.” Three sounds. When pronouncing this word, the speech apparatus performs three different functions for each of the three sounds. The sound, which is produced in the vocal cords and reaches the oral cavity, is formed when the tip of the tongue rises and touches the inner side of the upper front teeth, while the lower jaw slightly drops — thus forming the sound T.

When moving to the sound O, the lower jaw drops a little more, the upper and lower lips quickly change and protrude slightly forward, the space between them opens, the tongue rises slightly toward the soft palate, and the tip of the tongue is pulled back.

Now the last sound P. If P were at the beginning of a word, it would blend with the following sound as PY, for example in the word “Pyrak.” But since in the word “TOP” it stands at the end, it connects with the previous letter as YP. Therefore, when pronouncing P, the lower jaw remains slightly lowered, and the upper and lower lips are tightly pressed together. Thus, the word “TOP” is pronounced. The transition of the speech apparatus from one position to another should be quick and easy.

Example 2: Let us take the tongue twister:

“Ata says he will buy a horse for his grandson,

Apa says she will buy a piece of patterned fabric for her grandson.

Will the grandfather buy a horse?

Will the grandmother buy the patterned fabric?”

When pronouncing this tongue twister, the organs of the speech apparatus — the lower jaw, upper and lower lips, tongue, and oral cavity muscles — must move freely and actively. Each letter and word must be pronounced clearly and distinctly, without omitting any sounds. Since it is a tongue twister, it should also be spoken quickly.

The well-known stage speech pedagogue E. M. Chareli said:

“Every student, every future actor must pay special attention to learning the structure and control mechanism of the speech apparatus in order to master it properly.” [2, p. 335]. The control mechanisms of the speech apparatus are divided into two parts:

Central, and Peripheral.

The central part includes the brain and spinal cord, while the peripheral part includes the larynx, vocal cords, and other organs of speech. The physiological functions of these two parts are closely connected, as the central part directly regulates and coordinates the activity of the peripheral part.

The human brain’s anatomy is highly complex. It consists of three parts:

Two large hemispheres,

The medulla oblongata,

The cerebellum.

The large hemispheres contain more than five billion nerve cells, which is more than half of all the nerve cells in the human body. Since the nerve centers responsible for breathing, heart function, the pharynx, and facial muscles are located in the medulla oblongata, the work of the tongue, oral muscles, and jaw muscles, as well as eye protection reflexes, digestion, and heart functions, all depend on this part. Therefore, when the function of the brain is disturbed, the work of the speech apparatus also changes.

2. Breathing.

Proper breathing is very important for humans. Breathing is a natural law of human anatomy and physiology; it is the process of air exchange. By training various breathing and sound production techniques, future performers strengthen their breathing, voice, sound articulation, and speech apparatus, which allows them to deliver meaningful, expressive, and beautiful speech that deeply impacts the audience — this is the main purpose of stage speech.

During training, it is important to distinguish between two types of breathing: physiological and phonational.

1. Physiology — the function of the organism and the laws that regulate it.

2. Phonation — the articulation of speech sounds as a result of the activity of the speech organs. Drawing upon the many years of experience of stage speech specialists and phoniatic doctors, E. M. Chareli, who devoted his life to the training, development, and, when necessary, treatment of the voice, distinguishes the following types of breathing:

Physiological Breathing vs. Phonational Breathing:

Physiological Breathing:

- A person breathes involuntarily, automatically.

- The duration of inhalation and exhalation is approximately equal.

- The breathing pattern is as follows: inhale – exhale – pause – inhale again.

Phonational Breathing:

- A person consciously controls the breathing process and breathes deliberately.

- The inhalation is more frequent and shorter, while the exhalation, on the contrary, is slower and longer.

- The breathing pattern is as follows: inhale – exhale – speak between the two – inhale again.

According to I. P. Kozlyaninova and E. M. Chareli,

There are many difficulties when it comes to training the voice and phonational breathing. In most cases, attention is paid to the voice only when it becomes strained or is lost altogether. However, in order to train the voice properly, it is first necessary to identify the causes of voice disorders and apply appropriate treatment measures, which is not easy. Unfortunately, even in professional theatres, there is still widespread neglect toward the actor's speech voice." [3, p. 12]

This observation remains true to this day. Even in contemporary theatres and the field of television, the culture of speech often fails to meet professional standards. Beyond the phonational breath and vocal mastery, many actors still have poor diction (articulation), lack understanding of the law of harmony of sounds, and struggle to memorize their text — let alone interpret its deeper meaning.

Therefore, whether on stage, on screen, or on the radio, speech demands professional training and great responsibility.

During breathing, air passes through the respiratory tract into the lungs, providing the necessary oxygen supply. If the breathing process is disrupted, the respiratory system and lungs can develop diseases.

According to research conducted at the Leningrad Oncological Research Institute,

"One of the main causes of lung cancer is improper use of breath. Oncologists have proven that tumors develop in areas of the lungs where air does not reach — that is, in the parts not cleansed by air." [4, p. 5]

Thus, when the breathing process is disturbed, tumors may appear in parts of the lungs that are not supplied with air.

That is why it is essential to learn to fill the lungs completely with air and fully exhale it. However, to ensure sufficient oxygen supply, it is not necessary to take an excessively deep breath. Deep inhalation can put too much strain on the diaphragm and disrupt the natural rhythm of speech, making the voice sound unpleasant. Such tension is not only useless but also harmful — it causes the lungs to overexpand and the trachea to widen, potentially disturbing the physiological mechanism of breathing itself.

In general, learning to inhale and exhale fully serves two purposes:

1. It helps prevent lung diseases;
2. It allows control over the frequency and depth of breathing during physical training of the respiratory muscles.

According to E. Saricheva, breathing types are classified into four kinds:

1. Shoulder breathing,
2. Chest breathing,
3. Costal (intercostal) breathing,
4. Diaphragmatic breathing. [5, p. 78]

The reason one breath can take four different forms depends on the work of the body's muscles. Each type of breathing is determined by which respiratory muscles are engaged. For instance, in the first type, the shoulder muscles are active, causing the shoulders to rise and allowing breathing only through the upper part of the lungs. In chest breathing, the middle and upper parts of the lungs function. In intercostal breathing, the expansion of the ribs activates the diaphragm muscles during inhalation. In the fourth type — diaphragmatic breathing — the diaphragm contracts as much as possible, pushing the abdomen forward. At this moment, breathing through the lower part of the lungs becomes stronger. Combining all these leads to a genuine and proper mixed-diaphragmatic breathing, which is exactly what stage speech aims to develop — a natural, deep, and correct way of breathing.

E. M. Chareli identifies three main natural breathing patterns most commonly found in life:

- 1) Chest breathing
- 2) Abdominal breathing
- 3) Mixed-diaphragmatic (complete) breathing

The most important of these is mixed-diaphragmatic breathing. When breathing fully, the chest expands and the vocal passages open, allowing all the necessary muscles of the respiratory system to function properly. This type of breathing is the most effective model for developing voice and speech delivery.

3. Voice. The human voice is a complex phenomenon, still holding many mysteries. It depends not only on the function of certain muscles but also on the entire psychophysical apparatus of a person. Medicine has documented cases where individuals with no physical voice disorders lose their voices due to nervous breakdowns. Likewise, in daily life, we can easily observe how our mood affects our voice. When one is in a good mood, even difficult work feels lighter; similarly, physical relaxation and proper functioning of the speech apparatus significantly influence the rhythm and tone of speech. Anxiety disrupts breathing and, as a result, the rhythm of the voice. When the rhythm is disturbed, words lose their natural flow — sounds become unclear, making both the speaker and listener uncomfortable. The human voice should never sound artificial. If an actor does not train their voice properly, failure and even loss of voice are inevitable. The care of the voice must begin with proper maintenance.

Currently, one of the major issues in educational institutions and theaters is maintaining personal and vocal hygiene. Personal hygiene not only preserves health but also strengthens the vocal apparatus. An actor's mood, work efficiency, and creative inspiration largely depend on maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Proper sleep improves one's mental function, thought process, speech clarity, interpersonal communication, and helps maintain the ethical and aesthetic discipline of the stage. Conversely, lack of sleep disrupts the nervous system and negatively affects the voice. On the other hand, oversleeping weakens the immune system, making the body more susceptible to infections. Therefore, every student-actor must strictly follow both personal and vocal hygiene in daily life, on stage, and during training. For example, breathing and voice exercises

must be performed in clean, dust-free environments — otherwise, the harm outweighs the benefits.

Voice fulfills the primary expressive function of speech on stage. Through it, we understand (1) the theme of the play, (2) the emotions and thoughts of the character through tone, and (3) the psychological state of the character through vocal nuances. “The stage voice,” as noted by experts, “is a divine gift of nature — a sound created with feeling. It must never be artificial. The human voice should be light, bright, and pure, ringing like silver and flawless like gold. It must be flexible and agile enough to adapt to any rhythm or melody. Through its tones and nuances, it conveys the most delicate emotional and psychological shades of the human soul. Such a multifaceted, resilient voice is developed only through daily practice, discipline, and endurance, becoming immune to fatigue or strain. However, working with one’s voice is as difficult and meticulous as digging a well with a needle — requiring knowledge, competence, and literacy.” [6.18].

The functions of the speech apparatus, breathing, and voice are all closely linked to psychology. Speech generation is impossible without psychological mechanisms. Psychologically, speech is divided into two types: internal and external. Usually, spoken language (external speech) originates from thought (internal speech). The sharpness of an actor’s or student’s thinking reflects their professional skill and creative ability. The process of generating stage speech, especially in actor training, remains a complex topic requiring deep

research and creative exploration. Thus, reflections on generating stage speech will undoubtedly continue to serve as a foundation for future studies.

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